

Study of Vitellogenin Motif

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ABSTRACT

Vitellogenin (VTG) is known to be a female-specific protein and a precursor form of egg yolk. Three vitellogenin, Vtg I, Vtg II and Vtg III have been identified in chicken. Vitellinogen precursors supply the major egg yolk proteins which are a source of nutrients during early development of egg-laying (oviparous) vertebrates and invertebrates. A complete structural analysis and 3-D modelling of Vitellogenin protein of Chicken (Target), has been already done. The 1852 amino acid sequence of the Vitellogenin protein (Gallus gallus) was retrieved from NCBI database. OOPS model of Multiple EM for Motif Elicitation (MEME) online software package was used to carry out this analysis. Total fifteen amino acid sequences were taken for motif analysis. According to our results, Vitellogenin sequences, contains three motifs. We analyze that all fifteen sequences includes all three motifs but their start points are different. Motif investigation suggests that all selected VTG sequences from different resources have common conserved patterns.

KEYWORDS

MEME, Sequence Analysis, OOPS, Vitellogenin.

INTRODUCTION

Vitellogenin or VTG or VG (taken from Latin vitellus which means yolk and gener means to produce) is an identical term for the gene and the uttered protein. VTG belongs to a family of some lipid transport proteins. Vitellogenin (VTG) is known to be a female-specific protein and a precursor form of egg yolk [1]. VTG precursors offer the major egg yolk proteins that are a good source of nutrients during early stage development of oviparous, vertebrates and invertebrates. VTG precursors are the multi-domain apolipoproteins, which cleaved into different yolk proteins. In vertebrates, a vitellinogen protein is composed of an N-terminal signal peptide (for export) and four regions (that can be cleaved into yolk proteins lipovitellin-1 (LVI), phosvitin (PV), lipovitellin-2 (VII)), and a von-Willebrand factor type D domain (YGP40) [2,3]. VTG protein synthesis take place in the liver under the influence of estrogen [4] and included into the developing oocytes through blood circulation. Therefore, Vitellogenin has been used as a pointer for maturation of females [5,6,7] and for the early stage sex determination of several teleost fishes [8].

Vitellogenin protein, serve as a trace mineral transporting protein which actively mediate the transfer of these essential nutrients from liver of the hen to the ovary and developing oocyte, and therefore, to the yolk of the egg. Chicken Vitellogenin has been considered to be proteolytically cleaved into heavy and light chains namely lipovitellins and phosvitin respectively. These proteins are the major yolk granule proteins, during or after transportation into oocyte. Chicken α - and β -lipovitellin are derived from parent VTG proteins and have four subunits (125, 80, 40, and 30 kDa) and two subunits (125 and 30 kDa), respectively. In chicken, there are three vitellogenins, namely Vtg I, Vtg II and Vtg III have been characterized [9]. Amino acid analyses indicated the presence of a highly phosphorylated serine-rich phosvitin in Vtg I and Vtg II (116 mol of P) and of a low molecular weight phosphopeptide (phosvete) in Vtg III (44 mol of P). According to Wallace and Morgan [10], unfractionated phosvitin is composed of 5 major components known as B (MW 40000D), C (MW 33000D), E (MW 115000D) E (MW 218000D) and F (MW 13000D). According to the stoichiometric considerations it is suggested that vitellogenin I gives rise to phosvitins C and F; vitellogenin II gives rise to phosvitin B, whereas vitellogenin III gives rise to either phosvitin E1 or E2, but not E1 & E2. Another fourth one but yet undetected, Vitellogenin may also exist for the chicken [11]. Taborsky and Mok [12] firstly determined the molecular weights of minor and major phosvitin as 36KDa and 40KDa. Egg yolk phospho-protein is composed of phosvitin and phosvete. Phosvitin accounts for almost 60% of total egg yolk phosphoprotein and grasps about 90% of the egg yolk phosphorous. The meaning of phosvitin suggests that it carried high amount of phosphorous and its origin of egg yolk.

Analysis of motifs present in vitellogenin protein has been done by using MEME (Multiple EM for Motif Elicitation) analysis which is present on http://meme.nbcr.net/meme4_6_1/ (Fig. 1).

Figure-1: MEME overview

Materials and Methods

We have selected nineteen amino acids sequences of Vitellogenin protein from NCBI retrieved in a fasta format. [13]. OOPS model of MEME (Multiple Expectation Maximization for Motif

Elicitation) has been used for analysis of motifs present in given sequence. In MEME, output demonstrates color graphical alignment along with common regular expression of all possible motifs. The block represents start and end point of the sequences and demonstrates AA length. E-value explains the statistical significance of the motif. MEME (ver.3.5.7) [14] usually predict the most statistically significant (low *E*-value) motifs first. As per programming of MEME suite, it is designed for prediction of up to three motifs and they may be present in some or all of the input sequences. MEME decides the width and number of occurrence of each motif mechanically on the bases of low *E*-value of the motif—the likelihood of finding a uniformly well-conserved pattern in random sequences. By default software programming, only motif widths between six and fifty were considered, and MEME output is HTML and reveals the motifs as local multiple alignments of (subsets of) the given sequences, as well as in several other formats. Block diagrams of MEME suite, defines the relative positions of the motifs in each of the input sequences whereas, *E*-value describes an estimate of the expected number of motifs with the given log likelihood ratio (or higher) and with the same width and site count, that one would find in a likewise sized set of random sequences. Further, width describes that; each motif explains a specific pattern of a fixed sequence in which no gaps are allowed. In MEME package, sites define the conserved region present in the motifs. The number of sites is contributing to the construction of the motifs. In MEME suite, consequences also exhibit **information content** of the motif in bits, It is defines to the amount of the **uncorrected** information content, $R()$, in the columns of the LOGO. Motifs are characterized by position-specific probability matrices which are specifying the probability of each possible letter appeared at each probable position in an occurrence of the pattern (Motif). These are showed as "sequence LOGOS" includes stacks of letters at every position in the motif. The total height of the stack is known as the "**information content**" of that particular position in the motif (in bits). In case of proteins, the categories are based on the bio-chemical properties of the diverse amino acids.

Results and Discussion

In MEME suite, results display in the form of graph whereas sequences will exhibits in the form of sequence logo/regular expression (Table-2). Motif overview in figure-2 has shown 4.6e-649E-value of motif one, 8.3e-520E-value of motif two and 1.5e-494E-value of motif three. In Results were analyzed on the bases of *e*-value and *p*-value. Where second figure, describe about the conserved pattern of motifs and first one describe about the width of the same match. Higher *p*-value described the best match whereas lower the *e*-value better the results. By submitting multiple amino acid sequences to MEME suite, we find that all the sequences have everyone three motifs but the starts points of all these motifs are vary sequence to sequence. Figure no 3, 5 and 7 defines the number of site which contributing to the construction of the motif. In each protein sequence define the site in color format. These are shown aligned with each other. Each site is documented by the name of the sequence where it occurs, the strand, and the Start position in the sequence where the site begins. The sites are listed in increasing order based on statistical significance known as *p*-value. Figure 4, 6 and 8 shows that block diagram of each site and represent the motif location. The frequency of the motif in the protein sequences are exposed as colored blocks on a line. Motif one was present in seq. 9, 10, 7, 8, 3, 13, 12, 11, 6, 17, 15, 18 and 4. On the other hand, motif two is identified in seq.no 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18 and 19. On the bases of result analysis, Motif three present in seq. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18 and 19. The occurrence of motif has been displayed in combined block diagram (Figure-9) and might not be closely comparable as reported in each motif segment.

Table-1: Scientific name of different species

Seq. No.	Scientific Name
1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>

2	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>
3	<i>Macacacyclopis</i>
4	<i>Oryctolagusuniculus</i>
5	<i>Camelus dromedarius</i>
6	<i>Equuscaballus</i>
7	<i>Musmusculus</i>
8	<i>Susscrofa</i>
9	<i>Ovisaries</i>
10	<i>Capra hircus</i>
11	<i>Bostaurus</i>
12	<i>Bosindicus x Bostaurus</i>
13	<i>Bosindicus</i>
14	<i>Bosgrunniens</i>
15	<i>Rattusnorvegicus</i>

Sr. No.	Width/ Sites	E value	Logo	Regular expression
1	Width 50 Sites 19	4.6e-649		P[IF]KFEY[AT][NS]G[VR]VGK [IVL] [FY]AP[EA]G[VIC][SP] [TAD][TLM][VC]LNI[YHV]RGI [LV]N[IV]LQ[LI][NT]IKK[TS] QN[VI]Y[ED]LQE
2	Width 50 Sites 16	8.3e-520		[VA]DWM[KR]G[QK]TCG[LI] CGKADGE[VI]RQE[YF]RTPN[GE] R[VL]TKNAVS[FY]AHSW[VI]LP [AGS][EK]SCRD
3	Width 41 Sites 19	1.5e-494		G[VI]C[KHR]T[HLR]Y[VA]I[SQ] ED[AER]K[AN][ES]RIL[LV]TK[TS] [KR]V[DLN][NH]CQE[KR][IV]MK [DS][IV]G[LM]AY

Name	Start	p-value	Sites		
sequence9	10 5	1.22 e-58	TSALAAQL LT	PIKFEYANGVVGKVFAPAGVSAIVLNTIRGILNQLNKKI QNVYELQE	PGAQGVCK TH
sequence10	10 5	1.38 e-56	TSALAAQL LT	PIKFEYANGVVGKLFAPAGISTIVLNILRGIVNQLNKKI QNVYELQE	PGVQGICK TH
sequence7	10 5	1.38 e-56	TSALAAQL LT	PIKFEYANGVVGKLFAPAGISTIVLNILRGIVNQLNKKI QNVYELQE	PGVQGICK TH
sequence8	10 5	2.67 e-56	TSALAAQL MT	PIKFEYANGVVGKMFAPAGVSTIMVNLVYRGLNVLQNLKI KTHNVYELQE	AGAQGVCK KTL
sequence3	10 5	1.80 e-55	TQALAAQL LI	PIKFEYANGVVGKRVFAPAGVSAIVLNTIRGILNQLNKKI NQNYYELQE	AGAQTGCK TD
sequence12	10 5	4.76 e-55	TSALAAQL QI	PIKFEYANGVVGKVFAPAGVSPVTLNLRGILNQLNKKI TQNYELQE	AGAQGVCK TH
sequence13	10 5	6.82 e-55	TSALAAQL LT	PIKFEYANGVVGKIMAPAGISTIVLNILRGILNVLQNLKKI QNVYELQE	AGAQGVCK KTL
sequence11	10 5	3.92 e-54	MSTMIAE LQI	PIKFEYANGVVGKIFAPAGVSPVTLNLRGILNIFQLNKKI QNVYELQE	AGVQGVCK TH
sequence6	10 5	6.18 e-54	TSALAAQL LT	PIKFEYANGVVGKVFAPAGVSAIVLNTIRGILNQLNKKI QNVYELQE	PGVQGICK TH
sequence17	10 5	1.47 e-52	TSALSAQL LT	PIKFEYANGVVGKVFAPAGVSAIVLNTIRGILNIFQLNKKI MNVYDLQE	TGVKGVCK TS
sequence15	10 5	3.93 e-51	TTALATQL ST	PIKFEYANGVVGKRLAAPPVSTIVLNTIRGILNQLNKKI TQNVYEMQE	SGAHGVCK TN
sequence18	98 VL	8.70 e-51	KDALAPQL VL	PIKFEYANGVVGKLYAPEQIATVNLNIRGILNQLNKKI HKVYDLQE	VGTQGVCK TL
sequence4	10 5	9.60 e-51	TEALAAQL LI	PIKFEYANGVVG	

One

One

Name	Start	p-value	Sites		
sequence6	15 9	1.21e -49	VYELQEPGV Q	GICKTHYVISEDVKAERILLTKTKDLNNCQERIMKDIGL AY	TEKCVCEEA R
sequence10	15 9	4.21e -48	VYELQEPGV Q	GICKTHYVISEDVMAERILLTKTKDLNNCQERIMKDIGL AY	TEKCVCEES R
sequence7	15 9	4.21e -48	VYELQEPGV Q	GICKTHYVISEDVMAERILLTKTKDLNNCQERIMKDIGL AY	TEKCVCEES R
sequence9	15 9	6.81e -48	VYELQEPGA Q	GVCKTHYVISEDADADRILLTKTKDLNHCQERIVKDIGL AY	TERCVCEEA R
sequence13	15 9	1.79e -46	VYELQEAGA Q	GVCKTLVAIAEDEKAERILLTKSRDLNNCQEKIMKDIGL AY	TEKCIKCQQ N
sequence8	15 9	1.98e -44	VYELQEAGA Q	GVCKTLVAIAEDEKAERILLTKTRDLNHCQEKIMKDLG LAY	TEKCAKCQQ D
sequence3	15 9	5.22e -44	VYELQEAGA Q	GTCKTDYVISEDADAKAERIVTKSKDLNNCQERIMQDGM AY	TETCAHCQQ N
sequence1	15	1.06e	VYDLQEVGT	GVCKTLYSISEDARIENILLTKTRDMNNCQERIMKDMG	TEKCDKCCR

ame	Start	p-value	Sites
8	2	-41	Q LAY E
sequence1	15	4.22e-41	VYEMQESGA GVCKTNYVIREDARAERILTLTKTKDLNHCQEKIMKAIG VEKCHDCEA
5	9	-41	H LEH R
sequence1	15	5.77e-41	VFDLQEVGT GVCKTLYSISEDARNENILLTKTRDLNNCQERLIKDMGL TQKCERCQE
6	9	-41	Q AY E
sequence1	15	1.07e-40	IYDLQEEGV CVCRTQVAITENEKTERILLTKSRNLNQCQEKVMKDIG TKTSHKYQQ
9	8	-40	Q LAY D
sequence1	15	1.99e-40	VYELQEAGI GICHARYVIQEDRKNRSRIVYTRIVDLNNCQEKVQKSIG IYPCPVDVM
9	9	-40	G MAY K
sequence1	15	8.15e-40	IYELQEAGV GVCRTHYVISSESKANHITVTKSKDLSHCQERITKDFGL TEKCDCTE
1	9	-40	Q AY R
sequence2	15	1.48e-39	VYELQEAGI GVCBTRHYVIQEDRKNRSRVSVTKTVDQNNCQEKVIKSVG IYPCPVDMM
9	9	-39	G MAY K
sequence1	15	2.19e-39	IYELQEAGA GVCRTHYVISSEPKANHITVTKSKDLSHCQERIVKDVRL TERCAECTE
2	9	-39	Q AY R
sequence1	80	1.25e-38	VYELQEAGI GVCBARYVIQEDRKNRSRIFVTKTVDSTNCQEKVEKSVG IYPCPVDMM
4	80	-38	G MAY K
sequence5	80	1.25e-38	VYELQEAGI GVCBARYVIQEDRKNRSRIFVTKTVDSTNCQEKVEKSVG IYPCPVDMM
5	80	-38	G MAY K
sequence4	16	1.97e-36	ACAQGICKT YVISEDAVISAKAERIVITKSKDLNCHERIMKDIGMA TETCAQSQQ
5	5	-36	D Y R
sequence1	15	9.95e-34	VYDLQETGV GVCKTSYVLKEDPKADRLHLTKTTDLNLCTEKINMDVGC YTNKCEECV
7	9	-34	K MAG R

three

C

Figure 4.15 Block Diagram of Vitellogenin Proteins Motif 1

Figure 4.16 Block Diagram Of Vitellogenin Proteins Motif 2

Figure 4.17 Block Diagram Of Vitellogenin Proteins Motif 3

Combined Block Diagrams

Non-overlapping sites with a p-value better than 0.0001.
 The height of the motif "block" is proportional to $-\log(p\text{-value})$, truncated at the height for a motif with a p-value of $1e-10$.
 Click on any row to highlight sequence in all motifs. The motif blocks have tool tips with more information.

Conclusion

MEME suites developers provide an easy accessible tool for Motif analysis to the researcher community, who are interested in analyzing sequences of nucleic acids and proteins. At last, Our research explain that using multiple motifs gives much better database search results than using single motifs. Multiple motifs have more information about the quality of the protein family than do single motifs. On the bases of results, the present study suggests that Vitellogenin sequence of different species has same conserve region or patterns. On the base of our result we assumed that vitellogenin show similar function in all species. As per analysis of results, it describes that although vitellogenin presents in different source of origin, they contains common patterns of amino acids. It is again well-known fact that motifs may overlap with one another due to the reason of common consensus patterns.

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